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D6.2 Workshops report - 1

Project Acronym: ATHENA

Title: IMPLEMENTING GENDER EQUALITY PLANS TO UNLOCK RESEARCH POTENTIAL OF RPOS AND RFOS IN EUROPE

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¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GE	Gender equality
R+D+I	Research, Development and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation

Executive summary

The development of the Gender Equality Plans (GEP) as D4.4 by the ATHENA partners is a fundamental step towards the establishment of long-time conditions for equal opportunities of women and men in the science. The GEP is a strategic document and selected strategic stakeholders are expected to learn about it.

There are eight GEPs developed thanks to the ATHENA project and therefore we have organized eight local workshops with strategic stakeholders. Each workshop has been an open public event for interested stakeholders, such as professors, researchers, public authorities, etc. identified in Task 6.1.

The purposes of Workshop 1 under Task 6.2 is to present to the stakeholders the barriers and challenges and the solutions to overcome those encountered during the development of the GEPs and the activities that will be implemented thanks to the adoption of the GEPs. Thus the stakeholders have been involved in the further replication of the gender equity achievements under the ATHENA project to other appropriate communities.

The Agenda of each Workshop 1 under Task 6.2 has contained the next main elements:

- Official opening
- Presentation of ATHENA project
- Presentation of the WP2 outcomes
- Presentation of the GEP
- Open discussions
- Official closure

The duration of these workshops have been between 1 hour and 2 hours.

The speakers/moderators have been representatives of ATHENA project, who have been involved in the development of the GEPs and other project documents.

The venue was in: face-to-face format, virtual format or hybrid format.

The participants are described in Table 1 and they have been:

- **Academia and Research:**
 - academics from Research Funding Organizations;
 - academics from Research Performing Organizations;
 - representatives of Sister projects;
 - representatives of the University (internal staff and students);
- **Government & public sector (policy makers):**
 - representatives of the local authorities;
 - representatives of the regional authorities;
 - representatives of the national authorities;
- **Industry & business:**

- representatives of start-up incubators;
- representatives of STEM related companies;
- *Civil society:*
 - representatives of the associations, related to Gender Equity;
 - representatives of the Networks, related to Gender Equity;
 - representatives of the Non-Government Organizations, related to Gender Equity;
- *Media representatives.*

Table 1. General descriptions of the workshops at D6.2 under Task 6.2

Partner organization	Date of the Workshop 1 under Task 6.2	Number of stakeholders	Room
P2 – Institut Jozef Stefan (JSI, Slovenia)	15.09.2022	49	Hybrid
P3 – Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego W Kielcach (UJK, Poland)	28.06.2022 17.10.2022	7 15	Virtual Virtual
P4 – Universitatea Din Bucuresti (UB, Romania)	25.10.2022	34	Virtual
P5 – Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC, Canary Islands, Spain)	27.10.2022	38	Hybrid
P7 – Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej Akademie Vied (UVSK SAV, Slovakia)	28.03.2022	65	Virtual
P8 – University Of Ruse Angel Kanchev (URAK, Bulgaria)	10.06.2022	43	Face-to-face
P9 – Gobierno De Canarias (GOBCAN, Canary Islands, Spain)	16.06.2022	31	Hybrid
P10 – Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT, Azores, Portugal)	29.09.2022	34	Virtual
Total participants:		305	

In general we consider Workshop 1 under Task 6.2 as very successful, because:

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop: According to the project description at least 20 stakeholders are expected to participate each event, which means at least 180 for the entire consortium. As described in Table 1 we have managed to involve 305 of them. The overall attendance almost doubled our expectation. In

the case of Ruse University – the Minister of Education of Bulgaria was among the participants, too.

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion: After the presentation, there was interesting discussion. Most of the participants stood longer to discuss the future challenges.

Indicator #3: Emerging new cooperations: Thanks to the discussions some of the participants have decided to stay in contact with the host of the workshop for further replication of the GEPs in their organizations.

Each ATHENA partner has achieved **specific workshop results**, which are described in the next sections of this document. But all of them contribute to improve the equal opportunities between women and men in the related organizations.

Each workshop was followed by publications in mass media or social networks in internet and thus it supported our dissemination activities under WP7.

Some new names of stakeholders have been added to the project Database of stakeholders (D6.1).

In 2024 a second Workshop will be organized to demonstrate how promoting gender equality can unlock research potential, boosting the performance of the organizations and unlocking the research potential.

We are very thankful to all participants from the ATHENA consortium and the involved stakeholders for their contribution to improve the equal opportunities of women and men in the science.

SECTION 1. Workshop 1 report of Institut Jozef Stefan (JSI, Slovenia)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	GENDER EQUALITY, with awareness of diversity to an inclusive organizational culture
Date of the workshop	15-09-2022
Venue of the workshop	Jožef Stefan Intitute, Teslova 10, Ljubljana and https://zoom.us/j/92830641328 , Meeting ID 928 3064 1328
Names and positions of the speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dr. Romana Jordan, assistant director for EU affairs, JSI • prof. dr. Maja Remškar, researcher in the Department from solid state, JSI • prof. dr. Dunja Mladenič, head of the Department for Artificial Intelligence, JSI • prof. dr. Milica Antić Gaber, sociologist, Department of philosophy, Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana • dr. Vida Vukašinović, researcher in the Department for computer systems, JSI • prof. dr. Borka Jerman Blažič, ex-head of the Department for open systems and networks, JSI
Total of number of participants	<p>Total number of all participants: 57</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from ATHENA team: 8 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - speakers from ATHENA team: 3 - invited speakers from Academia and Research: 1 • Academia and Research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - academics from Research Funding Organizations: 0 - academics from Research Performing Organizations: 13 - representatives of Sister projects: 2 - representtaives of the University/Institute (internal staff and students): 30 • Government & public sector (policy makers): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the local authorities: 8 - representtaives of the regional authorities: / - representatives of the national authorities: 5

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry & business: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of start-up incubators: 0 - representatives of STEM related companies: 1 • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the associations, related to Gender Equity: 1 - representatives of the Networks, related to Gender Equity: 2 - representatives of the Non-Government Organizations, related to Gender Equity: 2 • Media representatives: 0
Participants from the ATHENA project partners	Number: 0

2. Agenda of the workshop

From – To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
14:00 – 14:10	1. Official opening and presentation of ATHENA project	dr. Romana Jordan, assistant director for EU affairs, JSI
14:10 – 14:25	2. Presentation of the WP2 outcomes	prof. dr. Maja Remškar, researcher in the Department for Solid State materials, JSI
14:25 – 14:35	3. Presentation of the GEP	prof. Dunja Mladenič, head of the Department for Artificial Intelligence, JSI
14:35 – 15:05	4. Challenges and solutions for gender equality in Slovenia: example from academia and science	prof. dr. prof. dr. Milica Antić Gaber, sociologist, Department of philosophy, Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana
15:05 – 15:25	5. Open discussion	dr. Vida Vukašinović, researcher in the Department for computer system, JSI
15:25 – 15:30	6. Official closure	Prof. dr. Borka Jerman Blažič, ex-head of the Department for open systems and networks, JSI

3. General description of the workshop

The workshop “GENDER EQUALITY, with awareness of diversity to an inclusive organizational culture” was held on 15 September at Jožef Stefan Institute with live as well as on line audience via zoom application. The workshop participants from different working environments expressed deep interest for resolving the

challenges in gender equality in science and academia through lively discussion that followed the workshop presentations.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The main goal of the workshop was to start mutual discussion with the stakeholders on the issue of gender equality in science and academia.

4.2 Achievement indicators

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop

The invitation for workshop was widely spread to different persons and 57 of them managed to participate. Detailed specification of participants is described in Chapter 1. The workshop took place in a hybrid form with 17 participants live and 40 participants via zoom. Among all participants, there were 27 stakeholders.

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion

After the presentation, there was lively and interesting discussion, focused mostly on the definition of gender equality, challenges and procedural aspects of GEP. Most of the participants stood longer to discuss the current and future challenges.

Indicator #3: Emerging new cooperations

Mutual cooperation was set with University of Ljubljana, Department of Philosophy.

4.3 Workshop results

The workshop speakers have provided information about the current results of the ATHENA project, among them the data collected with the survey and the interviews carried out with the JSI employees and with developed GEP content. Useful comments were received from the present stakeholders and the JSI employees that were among the workshop participants as they got better insight in the encountered challenges during the development of the GEP and the issues that will assure higher gender equality in science and research.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

Figure 1 Dr. Romana Jordan introduced the audience the Athena project.

Figure 2 Prof. dr. Maja Remškar summarised the situation in the field of gender equality at JSI.

Figure 3 Prof. dr. Dunja Mladenič presented challenges in implementation of gender equality plan at JSI.

Figure 4 The event took place in a hybrid form with 17 attendees live and 40 attendees via zoom.

Figure 5 Prof. dr. Milica Antić Gaber presented Challenges and solutions for gender equality in Slovenia: example from academia and science.

The event was promoted among all JSI employees via email and at the JSI webpage [JSI for gender equality](https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/EnakostSpolov). <https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/EnakostSpolov>

Conclusion

This workshop is a contribution to the overall efforts of the ATHENA consortium towards the envisaged results in the project description that are aimed to upgrade the gender equality in science, research and academia. Stakeholders were informed about the barriers and challenges and the solutions to overcome those encountered during the development of the GEP and the activities that will be implemented thanks to the adoption of the GEP.

SECTION 2. Workshop 1 report of Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego W Kielcach (UJK, Poland)

Section 2.1 Firsrts Workshop 1 report of Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego W Kielcach (UJK, Poland)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	Local workshop to discuss ATHENA outcomes in GEP with stakeholders
Date of the workshop	28/06/2022
Venue of the workshop	-name of your institution: Jan Kochanowski University -address: - -online: https://meet.google.com/osm-wmvk-xuf
Names and positions of the speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ana Kaminska, Phd – manager of the Athena project • Joanna Rudawska, Phd – Ombudsman of Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Total of number of participants	<p>Total number of all participants: 9</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from ATHENA team: 2 speakers; • Academia and Research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - academics from Research Funding Organizations: 0 - academics from Research Performing Organizations: 0 - representatives of Sister projects: 0 - representatives of the University (internal staff and students): 1

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government & public sector (policy makers): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the local authorities: 0 - representatives of the regional authorities: 0 - representatives of the national authorities: 0 • Industry & business: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of start-up incubators: 0 - representatives of STEM related companies: 4 • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the associations, related to Gender Equity: 2 - representatives of the Networks, related to Gender Equity: 0 - representatives of the Non-Government Organizations, related to Gender Equity: 0 • Media representatives: 0
Participants from the ATHENA project partners	Number: 0

2. Agenda of the workshop

From - To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
14:00 – 14:05	1. Official opening	Joanna Rudawska, PhD
14:05 – 14:35	2. Presentation of ATHENA project 3. Why GEP? - UE rules in Horizon Europe 4. Presentation of the GEP creation process (steps and useful tools)	Ana Kaminska, PhD
14:35 – 15:00	5. Presentation of UJK GEP main goals, tasks 6. Challenges in creation and implementation phase 7. What next – monitoring, improvement	Joanna Rudawska, PhD
15:00 – 15:30	8. Discussion	Joanna Rudawska, PhD
15:30 – 15:35	9. Official closure	Joanna Rudawska, PhD

3. General description of the workshop

UJK organizes meetings with stakeholders of the Athena project. One of them was held online on 28 June 2022. The invited organizations are foundations, companies. University employees also participated in the meeting. The participants were presented with the EC's concept of Gender Equality Plans, the process of their creation. Also presented were the goals and tasks set by Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce in this area. The participants unanimously agreed that gender equality is a good starting point for further discussion on counteracting other forms of discrimination such as age, disability, accessibility of services and others.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The main of the workshop was to start mutual discussion with the stakeholders on the issue of gender equality in research.

4.2 Achievement indicators

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop

According to the project description at least 20 stakeholders are expected to participate this event. We have managed to involve in the first meeting 6 of them, described in Chapter 1.

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion

After the presentation, there was interesting discussion. The discussion was moderated. The main issue was the identification of possible mutual benefits from the cooperation of partners and the aim to create a network of "external ambassadors" of equality.

Questions were asked about how the expertise of different stakeholders could be engaged and used to enrich, improve the GEP being implemented at UJK.

On the other hand, there was a discussion on how partner organisations (stakeholders) can benefit from good practices of the Athena project, how to get involved, how to use it to implement and disseminate equality solutions also in their institutions.

It was pointed out that not all the activities planned for implementation by the financial management institutions are well thought out. A lot of emphasis is put on gender equality, for example, some trainings are addressed to women, but they are not interested in them (forceful approach)

Indicator #3: Emerging new cooperations

- Mr Marcin Agatowski (You Can Do More Foundation) suggested that this is an area that needs to be incorporated and partnered with Social Service Centers.
- Mrs Isabella Przybysz suggested, providing information regarding the EC's plans, given her roles as an evaluator and expert on equality programs.
- Mrs Joanna Rudawska suggested organizing meetings with vocational schools that are predominantly boys and pointing out that this topic does not concern them.

4.3 Workshop results

All agreed that GEP is a good start to moving beyond gender. It is important to include other areas such as age equality, disability, access to infrastructure (including the internet) in these types of plans.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

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Conclusion

It is essential to have a broader discussion, invite more stakeholders and direct the conversation to other areas related to age, disability etc., starting from the area of science (because of the authority of the university and its rank) is a good idea.

Annexes

Kielce, 10.06.2022

Anna Depczyńska
Ośrodek Transferu Technologii
Politechnika Świętokrzyska

Szanowna Pani,

Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego w Kielcach w międzynarodowym partnerstwie wdraża projekt pn. ["ATHENA- Empowering female research talent through a gender equality infrastructure"](#) współfinansowany w ramach Programu Horizon 2020 (umowa ID: 101006416).

Projekt porusza ważny i aktualny temat redukcji barier w rozwoju kariery zawodowej bez względu na płeć, wdrażania usprawnień i dążenia do doskonałości organizacji.

Zadania w ramach projektu Athena pozwoliły na wypracowanie [Planu Równości Płci dla uczelni](#), który jest obligatoryjnym dokumentem dla organizacji, chcących aplikować o środki z programu Horyzont Europa a niebawem zapewne z innych programów i podmiotów.

Dlatego też chcielibyśmy zaprosić Panią do grona interesariuszy projektu, z którymi będziemy dzielić się dobrymi praktykami dotyczącymi zagadnień równości, przeciwdziałaniu dyskryminacji, wyrównywaniu szans, jak również czerpać od Państwa jako podmiotów zewnętrznych, aby jeszcze lepiej doskonalic procesy w organizacji.

Spotkanie odbędzie się 28.06. godz. 14.00 online. Link zostanie przesłany przed spotkaniem.

Osobą do kontaktu w przedmiotowej sprawie z ramienia projektu jest dr Joanna Rudawska (rzeczniczka UJK ds. równości płci) joanna.rudawska@ujk.kielce.pl, tel. +48 662 217 318.

Z poważaniem

dr Ana Kaminska
Wydział Prawa i Nauk Społecznych
Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego
w Kielcach

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Section 2.2 Second Workshop 1 report of Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego W Kielcach (UJK, Poland)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	Athena interesariusze _ Local workshop to discuss ATHENA outcomes in GEP with stakeholders
Date of the workshop	17/10/2022
Venue of the workshop	-name of your institution: Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce -address: - -online: Zoom https://us05web.zoom.us/j/87894722219?pwd=YnZnaDlndHdEeUZaNDRaM050Mm9JZz09
Names and positions of the speakers	Joanna Rudawska, Phd – Ombudsman of Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Total of number of participants	Total number of all participants: 16 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from ATHENA team: 1 speakers; • Academia and Research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - academics from Research Funding Organizations: 3 - academics from Research Performing Organizations: 0 - representatives of Sister projects: 0 - representatives of the University (internal staff and students): • Government & public sector (policy makers): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the local authorities: 3 - representatives of the regional authorities: 0 - representatives of the national authorities: 0 • Industry & business: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of start-up incubators: 0

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of STEM related companies: 3 • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the associations, related to Gender Equity: 6 - representatives of the Networks, related to Gender Equity: 0 - representatives of the Non-Government Organizations, related to Gender Equity: 0 • Media representatives: 0
Participants from the ATHENA project partners	Number: 0

2. Agenda of the workshop

From - To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
13:30 – 13:35	1. Official opening	Joanna Rudawska, PhD
13:35 – 14:00	2. Presentation of UJK GEP main goals, tasks 3. Challenges in creation and implementation phase 4. How to use a good practice 5. Training, materials, Athena portal	Joanna Rudawska, PhD
14:00 – 14:30	6. Discussion	Joanna Rudawska, PhD
14:35 – 14:40	7. Official closure	Joanna Rudawska, PhD

3. General description of the workshop

Athena project stakeholders meeting. The meeting was aimed at generating discussion whether GEPs will be/are needed by other organizations. Will there be a need to create plans for other programs like Erasmus, Interreg, national funds.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The main of the workshop was to start mutual discussion with the stakeholders on the issue of gender equality also in other areas, in other organizations not only academies.

4.2 Achievement indicators

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop :

According to the project description at least 20 stakeholders are expected to participate this event. We have managed to involve in the first meeting 6 of them (28.06.) and 15 participants from different environments on 17.10.2022

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion

The consensus was that every organization should have an internal equality plan that covers various areas. During the discussion, it was raised that applications from various programs are already evaluating the fulfillment of the condition of equality, accessibility. The GEP would make it easier for all applicants to justify their actions. It was also pointed out that UJK has gone through a long process. The complexity of the process of developing a GEP would depend on the size and specifics of the organization. Smaller ones don't need to have such a large document, but it's worthwhile to apply the EC's guidelines for the document like publicity, awareness raising, written, allocated budget at the beginning.

Indicator #3: Emerging new cooperations

- Mrs Anna Kuriata – Technology University in Kielce was interested in cooperation. The Technology University doesn't have a GEP yet. It is crucial to learn from sister university in Kielce.
- Mrs Monika Lewandowska – Digital Innovation Hub TKDIH, Kielce Technology Park was interested in trainings which UJK organizes for the staff. She would like to take part.
- Mrs Agnieszka Tercz – Education by Internet – mentioned that 17.11 there is planned activity targeted do women and Athena project should be part of it (Kielce City Hall is a host).

4.3 Workshop results

- All agreed that GEP will be needed in another project as Erasmus, Interreg etc.
- It should not be limited to the gender issues.
- It should be universal document showing responsibility of all organizations not only universities.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

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dr Joanna Rudawska
Rzecznik ds. Równości Płci
Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego w Kielcach

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Projekt

Zaangażowanie i wsparcie najwyższego kierownictwa

**Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego
w Kielcach partnerem projektu:**

*Athena – Implementing Gender
Equality to unlock research potential in
RPOs and RFOs – Horizon 2020*

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Uniwersytet
Jana Kochanowskiego
w Kielcach

ULPGC
Universidad de
Las Palmas de
Gran Canaria

INSTITUTE FOR
RESEARCH IN SOCIAL
COMMUNICATION SAS

Gobierno de Canarias
Comunidad de Economía,
Conocimiento y Empleo
Agencia Canaria de Investigación,
Innovación y Sociedad
de la Información

Dorota Domińczak

jrudawski

DOS AÇORES 2019-1-15-SU-7

Conclusion

It is essential to have a broader discussion, invite more stakeholders and direct the conversation to other areas related to age, disability etc. Starting from the area of science (because of the authority of the university and its rank) is a good idea.

Annexes

Invitation

Od: Joanna Rudawska jrudawska@ujk.edu.pl
Temat: Plan Równości - Athena interesariusze
Data: 13 października 2022 o 20:08
Do: Aga Tercz aga.tercz@epi.org.pl, agata.krzemien@epi.org.pl

Szanowne Panie,

Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego w Kielcach w międzynarodowym partnerstwie wdraża projekt pn. ["ATHENA- Empowering female research talent through a gender equality infrastructure"](#) współfinansowany w ramach Programu Horizon 2020 (umowa ID: 101006416).

Projekt porusza ważny i aktualny temat redukcji barier w rozwoju kariery zawodowej bez względu na płeć, wdrażania usprawnień i dążenia do doskonałości organizacji.

Zadania w ramach projektu Athena pozwoliły na wypracowanie [Planu Równości Płci dla uczelni](#), który jest obligatoryjnym dokumentem dla organizacji, chcących aplikować o środki z programu Horyzont Europa a niebawem zapewne z innych programów i podmiotów.

Dlatego też chcielibyśmy zaprosić Panią jako interesariusza projektu na spotkanie, które odbędzie się **17.10. godz. 13.30 (poniedziałek) online**. Spotkanie odbędzie się na platformie Zoom.

Plan spotkania

- Wprowadzenie Projekt Athena
- Plany Równości Płci i ich rola w aplikowaniu o środki na realizację projektów
- Plan Równości Płci Uniwersytetu Jana Kochanowskiego w Kielcach - dobra praktyka
- Uwagi, rekomendacje

Temat: Athena interesariusze
Czas: 16 paź 2022 01:30 PM Warszawa

Dołącz do spotkania Zoom
<https://us05web.zoom.us/j/87894722219?pwd=YnZnaDlndHdEeUZaNDRaM050Mm9JZz09>

Identyfikator spotkania: 878 9472 2219
Kod dostępu: 70BsJy

Do zobaczenia!

Z poważaniem
dr Joanna Rudawska
Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego w Kielcach
Wydział Prawa i Nauk Społecznych
Katedra Zarządzania
jrudawska@ujk.edu.pl
tel.: +48662217318

Znajdź mnie na:
[LinkedIn](#)
[ResearchGate](#)
[FB](#)

Projekty:
ATHENA [Gender equality to unlock research potential](#), Horizon 2020
Financen_LAB [Digital Simulator for Entrepreneurial Finance](#) Erasmus +
INTERGEN II [The intergeneration family businesses](#) - international consortium (2021-2024)
INTERGEN I [The intergeneration family businesses](#) - international consortium (2018-2020)

SECTION 3. Workshop 1 report of Universitatea Din Bucuresti (Romania)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	"Action plan regarding the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities between women and men – Consultative dialogue about the elaboration and implementation of measures to promote gender equality"
Date of the workshop	25/10/2022
Venue of the workshop	-name of your institution: University of Bucharest -address: WebEx meeting - https://anes.webex.com/anes/j.php?MTID=m213734f4a25bfb2429f754ef54fbb24b
Names and positions of the speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diana Elena Neaga, Adviser to the President, ANES • Laura Grünberg, Project Director, ATHENA-UB • Carmen Niculescu, Senior Adviser, ANES • Corina Ilinca, Quantitative Research Coordinator, ATHENA-UB • Alex Dinu, Expert, CALIPER Project - UEFISCDI • Roxana Marinescu, Human Resources Director GEP, ASE
Total of number of participants	<p>Total number of all participants: 37</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from ATHENA team: 4 , 2 speakers; • Academia and Research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - academics from Research Funding Organizations: 0 - academics from Research Performing Organizations: 8 - representatives of Sister projects: 1 - representatives of the University (internal staff and students): 5 • Government & public sector (policy makers):

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the local authorities: 1 - representatives of the regional authorities: 1 - representatives of the national authorities: 8 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry & business: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of start-up incubators: 0 - representatives of STEM related companies: 0 • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the associations, related to Gender Equity: 3 - representatives of the Networks, related to Gender Equity: 2 - representatives of the Non-Government Organizations, related to Gender Equity: 2 -National Unions-2 • Media representatives: 0
Participants from the ATHENA project partners	Number: 0

2. Agenda of the workshop

From - To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
14:00 – 14:15	Official opening	Diana Elena Neaga, Adviser, ANES Laura Grünberg, Project Director, ATHENA-UB
14:15 – 14:40	The implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and treatment for women and men in public and private institutions and organisations	Carmen Niculescu
14:40 – 14:55	The Gender Equality Plan – University of Bucharest	Corina Ilinca
14:55 – 15:05	Insights from the GEP elaboration and implementation process – UEFISCDI	Alex Dinu

15:05 – 15:20	Insights from the GEP elaboration process and future steps – ASE	Roxana Marinescu
15:20 – 16:05	Open discussions	Diana Elena Neaga (moderator)
16:05 – 16:10	Official closure	Diana Elena Neaga Laura Grunberg

3. General description of the workshop

The aim of this workshop was to create a beneficial environment for the sharing of expertise and for open exchanges of experience regarding the implementation of the principle of GE in Romanian institutions

The official opening provided an introduction to the subject matter and re-stated the meeting's objective.

ANES offered a comprehensive exposition of the national legislative framework pertaining to the implementation of the GE principle in public and private institutions, and delineated the obligations that all employers have in this regard.

The ATHENA-UB team displayed UB's GEP to the stakeholders, sharing relevant research findings, details about ongoing and completed activities, as well as upcoming steps.

This was followed by two institutions sharing their own experiences in developing GEPs, voicing the main lessons learned and the challenges expected moving forward.

Finally, the open dialogue session provided opportunities for other participants to contribute ideas and opinions on the subject matter and to address the main difficulties arising from this process.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The main of the workshop was to start mutual discussion with the stakeholders on the issue of gender equality in research.

4.2 Achievement indicators

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop

According to the project description at least 20 stakeholders are expected to participate this event. We have managed to involve 37 of them, described in Chapter 1.

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion

After the presentation, there was interesting discussion. Most of the participants stood longer to discuss the future challenges. Topics included: budgetary restraints, danger of producing just documents and not concrete actions, types of institutional resistance, how to obtain long term sustainability of the GEPs in the context of cycles of elections within each institutions.

Indicator #3: Emerging new cooperations

In terms of future concrete cooperations during the meeting representative of the Syndicate ask for present experts in the meeting to come and present their GEPs and for representative of ANES to involve them in future consultations. Representative of the University of Constanta invite UB, AE and UEFISCDI to a future meeting with academic institutions for continuing sharing experiences. ANES promise to organize future similar meetings periodically for enlarge the network of stakeholders.

4.3 Workshop results

During the workshop, many experiences, challenges, issues and questions were brought forward, by presents and participants, which provided valuable information to the ATHENA-UB team, as we move forward with the next steps in the implementation of the GEP.

Possible future collaboration appeared as well as concrete suggestions for the implementation of UB plan (for example the idea of externalizing somehow the evaluation process of the implementation of the PEG and to include in GEPI representatives from all faculties). ANES also clarified a number of legal aspects (concerning the official approval they give to each plan, the procedure to obtain it, and how the GEPs could be included in future Diversity Plans requested by the EU).

The most precious result is the initiation of the network of supporters of GEPs in Romania.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

Media releases:

<https://gep.unibuc.ro/stakeholders-workshop/>

<https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=138446528935981>

athena
gender equality to unlock
research potential

01:03:41

María-Ramona Coleasă

Implementarea principiului egalității de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați

AGENTIA NAȚIONALĂ PENTRU EGALITATEA DE ȘANSE ÎNTRE FEMEI ȘI BĂRBAȚI

La nivelul instituțiilor și organizațiilor publice și private

24°C Sunny

25.10.2022

01:37:32

María-Ramona Coleasă

ANES Conferința (gazdă)

Domeniile prioritare

1. Leadership pentru egalitate de gen

2. Guvernanta pentru egalitate de gen

3. Resurse Umane (Recrutare, Promovare, Retenție)

4. Integrarea dimensiunii de gen în conținuturile programelor academice interdisciplinare

5. Echilibrul viață profesională-viață privată, responsabilități de îngrijire

6. Prevenirea și combaterea hărțurii sexuale și a discriminării de gen

7. Comunicare instituțională pentru promovarea egalității de gen

8. Integrarea dimensiunii de gen în conținuturile programelor academice

25°C Sunny

14:54

25.10.2022

www.athenaequality.eu

Conclusion

During this workshop, the ATHENA-UB team had the opportunity to present, for the first time, the institution's new Gender Equality Plan as an example of good practice in front of members of other significant institutions in the research and education sector and in the administrative sector. The feedback received was very positive, with stakeholders appraising the comprehensive approach of the Plan.

The workshop attained its objective, as stakeholders had the chance to receive practical information about the legal framework in which the principle of GE can be promoted, witness candid sharings of experience regarding the actual steps of the elaboration and implementation of a GEP, as well as raise and address questions and practical concerns.

Annexes

AGENȚIA NAȚIONALĂ
PENTRU EGALITATEA DE ȘANSE
ÎNTRE FEMEI ȘI BĂRBAȚI

În cadrul evenimentului, Universitatea București, va prezenta ca model de bună practică, *Planului de Egalitate de Gen al Universității din București (GEPI-UB)*, membrii echipei implicate în realizarea acestui document urmând să împărtășească celor interesați, atât etapele parcurse, experiențele procesului de elaborare și structurare a planului, cât și problemele întâmpinate.

Vă invităm la acest dialog, alături de alte instituții publice din România, atât din sfera administrativă cât și din cea academică pentru realizarea unui schimb util de experiență pentru buna desfășurare a activităților de elaborare și implementare a planurilor de acțiune privind egalitatea de gen.

Accesul la eveniment se va realiza în urma confirmării participării, pe baza link-ului de acces pe platforma Webex, ce va fi transmis ulterior, de către ANES.

Pentru confirmarea participării dumneavoastră, precum și dacă doriți să prezentați în cadrul evenimentului planul de acțiuni pentru implementarea principiului egalității de gen elaborat la nivelul instituției pe care o reprezentați, avem rugămintea să ne transmiteți un mesaj în acest sens, pe adresele de e-mail: cabinet@anes.gov.ro și laura.grunberg@unibuc.ro

Cu deosebită considerație

Luminița Popescu

Secretar de stat

Intrarea Camil Petrescu nr.5, Sector 1, București
Tel.: +4 021 313 00 59
secretariat@anes.gov.ro www.anes.gov.ro

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gender equality to unlock
research potential

AGENȚIA NAȚIONALĂ
PENTRU EGALITATEA DE ȘANSE
ÎNTRU FEMEI ȘI BĂRBAȚI

INVITAȚIE

***"Planul de acțiune privind implementarea principiului egalității de șanse între femei și bărbați –
Dialog consultativ privind elaborarea și implementarea măsurilor
pentru promovare a egalității de gen"***

Stimată doamnă/ Stimate domn,

Agencția Națională pentru Egalitatea de Șanse dintre femei și bărbați (ANES) are deosebita plăcere de a vă adresa invitația de participare la evenimentul "*Dialog consultativ pentru realizarea planurilor de acțiune privind implementarea principiului egalității de șanse între femei și bărbați*" ce va fi organizat on-line, marți, 25 octombrie 2022. Evenimentul este organizat în colaborare cu Universitatea București, în contextul implementării Planului de Egalitate de Gen din cadrul *Universității din București (GEPI-UB)*, document realizat în concordanță atât cu cerințele naționale, cât și cu cele europene.

Evenimentul are ca obiectiv formularea de recomandări privind elaborarea *Planului de acțiune privind implementarea principiului egalității de șanse între femei și bărbați*, document prevăzut în legislația actuală, respectiv Legea nr.202/2002 a egalității de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați, republicată. Acest document se referă la adoptarea, la nivelul fiecărei instituții publice sau angajator, a unor măsuri active de promovare a egalității de gen și eliminarea discriminării directe și indirecte după criteriul de gen, precum și măsuri privind prevenirea și combaterea hărțuirii la locul de muncă, măsuri privind egalitatea de tratament în ceea ce privește politica de remunerare, promovare în funcții și ocuparea funcțiilor de decizie. Planurile de acțiune privind implementarea principiului egalității de șanse între femei și bărbați se elaborează conform prevederilor H.G. nr.262/2019, pentru aplicarea normelor metodologice de aplicare a prevederilor legii nr.202/2002 și fiind avizate de către ANES, în calitate de autoritate guvernamentală care asigură fundamentarea, elaborarea și aplicarea strategiei și politicilor Guvernului în domeniul egalității de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați, având în același timp rolul de a monitoriza aplicarea și respectarea prevederilor legale în domeniu.

Intrarea Camil Petrescu nr.5, Sector 1, București
Tel.: +4 021 313 00 59
secretariat@anes.gov.ro www.anes.gov.ro

SECTION 4. Workshop 1 report of Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC, Canary Islands, Spain)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	Gender equality and research and transfer at the ULPGC
Date of the workshop	27/10/2022
Venue of the workshop	-name of your institution: ULPGC -address: Aula de Piedra, Sede Institucional de la ULPGC. C/ Juan de Quesada, 30, 35001
Names and positions of the speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carolina Mesa Marrero, Director of Equality of the ULPGC • Aridane González González, Director of Research and Technological Development of the ULPGC • Carmen Grau Pineda, Director of Faculty of the ULPGC • Marlene Santacruz, EU Project Manager at Consulta Europa • Yaiza Gómez Yáñez, Project Manager and Researcher – ATHENA project • Researches: Beatriz González López-Valcárcel, María Zoraida Sosa Ferrera, María Teresa Cáceres Lorenzo, María Cristina Carmona Duarte y Elena Carretón Gómez.
Total of number of participants	<p>Total number of all participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from ATHENA team: 3 speakers; • Academia and Research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - academics from Research Funding Organizations: - academics from Research Performing Organizations: 2

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of Sister projects: - representatives of the University (internal staff and students): 29 • Government & public sector (policy makers): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the local authorities: 1 - representatives of the regional authorities: 1 - representatives of the national authorities: • Industry & business: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of start-up incubators: - representatives of STEM related companies: 1 • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the associations, related to Gender Equity: 3 - representatives of the Networks, related to Gender Equity: - representatives of the Non-Government Organizations, related to Gender Equity: 1 • Media representatives: 1
<p>Participants from the ATHENA project partners</p>	<p>Number: 3</p>

2. Agenda of the workshop

From - To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
10:00 – 10:10	1. Official opening	Carolina Mesa Marrero, Director of Equality of the ULPGC Aridane González González, Director of Research and Technological Development of the ULPGC
10:10 – 10:20	2. Presentation of ATHENA project	Marlene Santacruz, EU Project Manager at Consulta Europa
10:20 – 10:40	3. The importance of gender equality plans as a tool to move towards effective equality within the framework of research	Carmen Grau Pineda, Director of Teaching Staff at the ULPGC and professor Holder of Labor and Social Security Law of the ULPGC
10:40 – 11:00	4. Measures foreseen in research and transfer in the II gender equality plan of the ULPGC	Carolina Mesa Marrero, Director of Equality of the ULPGC
15:00 – 15:40	5. Workshop on Equality and Research: a view from different branches of knowledge	Beatriz González López-Valcárcel, María Zoraida Sosa Ferrera, María Teresa Cáceres Lorenzo, María Cristina Carmona Duarte y Elena Carretón Gómez.
15:40 – 15:45	6. Official closure	Carolina Mesa Marrero, Director of Equality of the ULPGC

3. General description of the workshop

The main objective of this workshop is to address the relevance of gender equality plans in the field of research and transfer, and to present the measures in this field included in the II Gender Equality Plan of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria and its relationship with the rest of the measures included in the GEP.

Likewise, a debate will be held about the difficulties encountered by women researchers in the development of their professional career. To this end, there will be the presence of female researchers from the ULPGC, belonging to various branches of knowledge, who will show their experience and opinion on these issues.

For this reason, entities and people from the community related to science, research and innovation in the Canary Islands, as well as those linked to gender equality in the Canary Islands, were invited to attend the event so that they could contribute to the debate.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The main objective of this workshop is to address the relevance of gender equality plans in the field of research and transfer, and to present the measures in this field included in the II Gender Equality Plan of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria and its relationship with the rest of the measures included in the GEP.

4.2 Achievement indicators

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop

According to the project description at least 20 stakeholders are expected to participate this event. We have managed to involve 38 of them, described in Chapter 1. However, the number of invitations does not correspond to the large number of invitations that we have carried out. We have created a specific email for the Athena Project (proyectoathena@ulpgc.es) in order to make the invitation more attractive and we have also created a poster. More than 250 invitations were sent, through email, phone calls and invitations through other entities.

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion

After the presentation, there was interesting discussion. Most of the participants stood longer to discuss the future challenges. The topics were the following:

- What are the main difficulties you have had in advancing your career as researchers?
- What other measures, in the field of research and transfer, could be included in the Gender Equality Plan of the ULPGC?
- Law 17/2022, of September 5, which modifies Law 14/2011, on Science, Technology and Innovation, has recently been approved. Among the most relevant developments, in the field of research, the implementation of measures to achieve effective and real equality between women and men is planned. Among other measures, it is worth mentioning the establishment of programs to support the advancement of women in research careers in equal conditions to avoid abandonment and so that they can progress in equal conditions with men (which may include information actions, training, advice, mentoring, visibility, establishment of

support networks, or promotion of good practices in conciliation and mobility); Specific positive action measures in favor of women, to correct situations of de facto inequality with respect to men, especially in the degrees and higher levels of the research career; programs to promote innovative entrepreneurship for women; measures to promote co-responsibility to promote the overcoming of traditional gender roles.

- What assessment do you make (according to your experience) of this type of measures and, in particular, if they could solve inequalities, disadvantages and obstacles?

These questions were answered by the speakers and this allowed people from both the public and the online attendees to launch different questions and contributions.

Indicator #3: Emerging new cooperations

Create relationships with the Island Council of Gran Canaria, to carry out training and new events. As well as new events and discussion forums on gender equality and research with other entities.

4.3 Workshop results

We obtained good results since numerous online and face-to-face guests participated. The participation of the online and physical public gave rise to new proposals in terms of conciliation and co-responsibility, improvements in communication and visibility of equality and improvement in that equality measures are more concrete solutions to respond to the real problems of societies.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

Dissemination of the event: <https://www.ulpgc.es/noticia/2022/10/27/unidad-igualdad-organiza-workshop-igualdad-genero-e-investigacion-y-transferencia>

Conclusion

As the first workshop organized by the UPLGC as a partner of the Athena project, the results have been better than expected. This will allow us to organize future events more efficiently and we hope that in the future we can count on more attendees.

Annexes

I. Invitation to the stakeholders in Spanish:

Buenas tardes,

Nos complace invitarle al workshop organizado por la Unidad de Igualdad de la ULPGC en el marco del proyecto ATHENA: "Igualdad de Género e Investigación y Transferencia en la ULPGC", que tendrá lugar en formato híbrido (presencial y online) el próximo día 27 de octubre de 2022, a las 10:00 am (hora canaria), en el aula de Piedra de la Sede Institucional de la ULPGC, y en formato online.

Uno de los objetivos principales del proyecto ATHENA es apoyar a las organizaciones participantes, entre ellas la ULPGC, en el desarrollo e implementación de Planes de Igualdad, destinados a lograr una participación equitativa entre mujeres y hombres y a eliminar todo tipo de discriminación por razón de género que pueda existir en el seno de estas organizaciones, así como potenciar la participación de mujeres en el ámbito de la investigación, desarrollo e innovación.

Este workshop tiene como objetivo principal abordar la relevancia de los planes de igualdad en el ámbito de la investigación y transferencia, y presentar las medidas en este ámbito incluidas en el II Plan de Igualdad de la ULPGC. Asimismo, se llevará a cabo un debate acerca de las dificultades con las que se encuentran las mujeres investigadoras en el desarrollo de su carrera profesional. Para tal fin, se contará con la presencia de mujeres investigadoras de la ULPGC, pertenecientes a varias ramas del conocimiento, que mostrarán su experiencia y opinión en estos temas.

Por este motivo, se le invita como integrante de la comunidad relacionada con la ciencia, la investigación y la innovación en Canarias a asistir al evento para que pueda contribuir al debate. Nos gustaría que le pudiera dar traslado de esta invitación al resto de personas integrantes de su proyecto al objeto de que puedan acudir al mismo.

Puede encontrar la agenda del evento en adjunto.

Para una adecuada organización del evento y por límites de aforo, le rogaríamos respondiese a este correo electrónico, antes del 24 de octubre, confirmando su participación de forma presencial u online al mismo. Aquellas personas que confirmen su asistencia online recibirán días antes del evento el enlace de teams.

Si quiere conocer más sobre el proyecto ATHENA puede visitar el siguiente enlace: <https://www.athenaequality.eu/>

II. Image of the workshop:

III. Agenda of the event:

WORKSHOP AGENDA

Igualdad de Género e Investigación y Transferencia en la ULPGC

Fecha: 27 de octubre de 2022

Presencial: Aula de Piedra, Sede Institucional de la ULPGC.
C. Juan de Quesada, 30, 35001

Online: el enlace se remitirá a quienes confirmen su asistencia online

10.00h – 10:10h	<p>Bienvenida</p> <p>Aridane González González, Director de Investigación y Desarrollo Tecnológico de la ULPGC</p> <p>Carolina Mesa Marrero, Directora de la Unidad de Igualdad de la ULPGC</p>
10:10h – 10:20h	<p>Presentación del Proyecto Horizonte 2020 'ATHENA'</p> <p>Marlene Santacruz – EU Project Manager de Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L.</p>
10:20h – 10:40h	<p>La importancia de los planes de igualdad como herramienta para avanzar hacia una igualdad efectiva en el marco de la investigación</p> <p>Carmen Grau Pineda, Directora de Profesorado de la ULPGC y profesora titular de Derecho del Trabajo y de la Seguridad Social de la ULPGC</p>
10:40h – 11:00h	<p>Medidas previstas en investigación y transferencia en el II plan de igualdad de la ULPGC</p> <p>Carolina Mesa Marrero, Directora de la Unidad de Igualdad de la ULPGC</p>
11:00 – 11:20	Break
11:20h – 12:25h	<p>Workshop en Igualdad e Investigación: una visión desde distintas ramas del conocimiento</p> <p>Intervención de mujeres investigadoras de la ULPGC representantes de varias ramas del conocimiento</p>
12.25h – 12:30h	<p>Clausura</p> <p>Carolina Mesa Marrero, Directora de la Unidad de Igualdad de la ULPGC</p>

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SECTION 5. Workshop 1 report of Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej Akademie Vied (UVSK SAV, Slovakia)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	Local workshop to discuss ATHENA outcomes in GEP with stakeholders Gender equality in the SAS: the journey and results of the gender audit
Date of the workshop	28/03/2022
Venue of the workshop	-name of your institution: UVSK SAV -address: Zoom online meeting: Launch Meeting - Zoom
Names and positions of the speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gabriel Bianchi, senior researcher (ATHENA) • Barbora Holubova, researcher (ATHENA) • Miroslava Šudila Žilinská, PhD student, project manager (ATHENA)
Total of number of participants	<p>Total number of all participants: 68</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from ATHENA team: 3 speakers; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia and Research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - academics from Research Funding Organizations: 0 - academics from Research Performing Organizations: 43 - representatives of Sister projects: 3 - representtaives of the institution (internal staff and students): 19 • Government & public sector (policy makers): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the local authorities: 0 - representtaives of the regional authorities: 0 - representatives of the national authorities: 13 • Industry & business: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of start-up incubators: 0 - representatives of STEM related companies: 0

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the associations, related to Gender Equity: 0 - representatives of the Networks, related to Gender Equity: 0 - representatives of the Non-Government Organizations, related to Gender Equity: 1 • Media representatives: 1
Participants from the ATHENA project partners	Number: 0

2. Agenda of the workshop

From - To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
14:00 – 14:05	1. Official opening	Barbora Lásticová (UVSK SAV director) Gabriel Bianchi, (researcher)
14:05 – 14:10	2. Presentation of ATHENA project	Gabriel Bianchi
14:10 – 14:30	3. Presentation of the WP2 outcomes	Gabriel Bianchi, Miroslava Šudila Žilinská (project manager) Barbora Holúbová (researcher)
14:30 – 15:00	4. Presentation of the GEP	Gabriel Bianchi, Miroslava Šudila Žilinská
15:00 – 15:55	5. Open discussions	Lucia Hargašová (researcher, administrative staff)
15:55 – 16:00	6. Official closure	Gabriel Bianchi,

3. General description of the workshop

The workshop consisted from 2 parts: 1. Presentation of the main results from the WP2 and the prepared GEP; 2. Discussion on the questions regarding gender audit, GEP, but also overall general discussion on what does it mean to achieve gender equality in science and what the appropriate measures to apply when researching gender equality in the institutions and share mutual experience from the GEP preparation and first weeks of implementation.

Approximately two weeks before the event, we disseminate the invitation through web announcement, social media and direct mails. We have identified about 42

stakeholders outside the institution which were directly invited through e-mail, mostly from the universities (e.g. teams involved in the GEPs preparations and sister projects) and public and government bodies. The invitation was also sent to the members of the SAS GEPI committee and the Commission for Equal Opportunities at the SAS who also shared the information. Also our member of AB resent the invitation to her colleague.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The main goal of the workshop was to start mutual discussion on the issue of gender equality in research in Slovak context. Although several HEIs in Slovakia have been developing their own GEPs, mutual discussions were missing. Our second aim was to introduce the issue within the whole institution of the Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS). After one year of gender audit, we knew representatives from the SAS would like to know more about the results and next steps.

4.2 Achieved indicators

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop

According to the project description at least 20 stakeholders are expected to participate this event. We have managed to involve more than 40 of them, described in Chapter 1. The overall attendance almost doubled our expectation.

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion

After the presentation, there was interesting discussion. Most of the participants stood longer to discuss the future challenges.

Indicator #3: Emerging new cooperations

After the event, two invites for future cooperations were initiated from the invited stakeholder. The first one was from the government equality body who is in charge of the national project on work-life balance. The other was an invite for cooperation during the GEP implementation from the largest Slovak university.

4.3 Workshop results

We evaluate the event as successful. The attendance was higher than expected. The event was not only important as a networking opportunity with the representatives from the HEIs, government and public institution but also on building the alliances within the institution. We had a chance to meet new colleagues who would like to engage in the issue, who are according to us the important agents in our journey for the institutional change.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

Presentation was recorded. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EDAy9ul6Msl>

Metodológia

Rodový audit v SAV

- Komparatívna metodológia pre celé konzorcium
- Analýza medzinárodných, národných a inštitucionálnych politík
- Rodová rovnováha:**
 - Kvantitatívne rodové indikátory
- Inštitucionálne nástroje podpory RR**
 - Kvalitatívne zhodnotenie
- Prieskum o vzťahoch medzi mužmi a ženami**
 - Dotazníkový prieskum
- Skúsenosti v súvislosti s rodovou rovnosťou**
 - Rozhovory
 - Fokusové skupiny

Kvantitatívne rodové indikátory

- Absolventi a absolventky
- Ženy a muži vo vedeckej profesii
- Kariérny rozvoj
- Ženy a muži v rozhodovaní a vedení
- Rodové aspekty pracovných podmienok
- Rodové aspekty vedeckých výstupov

6

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101056416

Plán rodovej rovnosti

Plán rodovej rovnosti SAV

Schválený v decembri 2021

Oblasť intervencie

- Rovnosť pracovného a súkromného života a organizačná kultúra
- Rodová rovnosť v oblasti výskumu a inovácie
- Rodová rovnosť v oblasti kariérneho rozvoja
- Integrácia rodového hľadiska vo výskume a výučbe

A ďalšie odporúčania pre Plán rodovej rovnosti SAV

- Povedomie o rodovej rovnosti
- Podpora mladých vedeckých pracovníčok a pracovníkov
- Používanie rodovo citlivého jazyka
- Monitoring

22

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101056416

Argumenty pre rodovú rovnosť

Prečo sa venovať rodovej rovnosti?

- Rodová rovnosť zvyšuje validitu a kvalitu vedeckých výstupov, pretože pomáha zohľadňovať rôznorodé hľadiská a prístupy.
- Rodová rovnosť vytvára lepšie pracovné podmienky, ktoré pomáhajú vytvárať kvalitné výsledky a využívať potenciál celého tímu.
- Rodová rovnosť je prevenciou mrhania a odchodu talentov.

3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101056416

Zášk: Generálne nariadenie pre výskum a inováciu (Európske komisie) (2021), Inštrukcia Európskej únie o plánovaní rovnosti pohlaví - Publikácia Úradu Európskej únie (europa.eu)

Conclusion

This event was our first attempt to meet with other stakeholders, both outside the Slovak Academy of Sciences but also institutes within the Academy (because all the institutes represent own legal entities, therefore we manage them as important stakeholders, too). We also wanted to meet researchers and representatives from the governmental

institutions who are participating in the gender equality issue so we can discuss with them challenges but also opportunities in the next years of implementation of the GEP.

Annexes

Online invitation for the event

https://www.sav.sk/?lang=sk&doc=services-news&source_no=20&news_no=10226

The screenshot shows the website of the Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAV). The main navigation bar includes: KARIÉRA, KONTAKTY, INTRANET, WEBMAIL, SKUPINY VIED, ČASOPIS AKADEMIA, and a search bar. The main menu highlights: O NÁS, UDALOSTI, VEDA A VÝSKUM, VZDELÁVANIE A ŠTIPENDIÁ, DOKUMENTY, and MÉDIÁ. The 'UDALOSTI' (Events) sidebar lists: Aktuality, Newsletter, Podujatia, and Konferencie. The main content area features a banner for 'ÚSTAVNÝ SEMINÁR' (Institutional Seminar) titled 'Rodová rovnosť v SAV: Cesta a výsledky rodového auditu' (Gender Equality in SAV: Path and Results of Gender Audit). The seminar is organized by the 'Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, v. v. i.' and features speakers: doc. PhDr. Gabriel Bianchi, CSc., Mgr. Barbora Holubová, PhD., and Mgr. Miroslava Šudila Žilinská. The date is 28. 3. 2022. Below the banner is a 'POZVÁNKA NA SEMINÁR' (Invitation to Seminar) section with detailed text in Slovak, including the seminar's purpose, topics, and contact information. At the bottom, there are logos for 'athenaequality.eu' and the European Union.

SECTION 6. Workshop 1 report of University Of Ruse Angel Kanchev (URAK, Bulgaria)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	Local workshop to discuss ATHENA outcomes in GEP with stakeholders
Date of the workshop	10/06/2022
Venue of the workshop	-name of your institution: University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev"(URAK, BG) -address: Kaneff Center at the University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev", 8 Studentska St., Ruse, Bulgaria
Names and positions of the speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nikolay Denkov, Minister of Education of Bulgaria • Hristo Beloev, Rector of URAK • Diana Antononva, Vice-Rector of URAK • Daniel Pavlov, URAK • Svilen Kunev, URAK • Svilena Ruskova, URAK • Ana Popova, URAK
Total of number of participants	<p>Total number of all participants: 50</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from ATHENA team: 7 <p>• Academia and Research:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - academics from Research Funding Organizations: 0 - academics from Research Performing Organizations: 21 - representatives of Sister projects: 0 - representtaives of the University (internal staff and students): 4 <p>• Government & public sector (policy makers):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the local authorities: 3 - representtaives of the regional authorities: 6 - representatives of the national authorities: 1 <p>• Industry & business:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of start-up incubators: 0 - representatives of STEM related companies: 0 • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the associations, related to Gender Equity: 7 - representatives of the Networks, related to Gender Equity: 0 - representatives of the Non-Government Organizations, related to Gender Equity: 0 • Media representatives: 1
Participants from the ATHENA project partners	Number: 0

2. Agenda of the workshop

From - To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
12:00 – 12:05	1. Official opening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nikolay Denkov, Minister of Education of Bulgaria • Hristo Beloev, Rector of URAK
12:05 – 12:10	2. Presentation of ATHENA project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Svilena Ruskova, URAK
12:10 – 12:15	3. Presentation of the WP2 outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diana Antononva, Vice-Rector of URAK
12:15 – 12:40	4. Presentation of the GEP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daniel Pavlov, URAK
12:40 – 12:55	5. Open discussions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Svilen Kunev, URAK

3. General description of the workshop

The Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev" was officially presented to external stakeholders on June 10, 2022 in a special Round Table dedicated to avoiding discrimination.

The **Minister of Education and Science of Bulgaria**, as well as the Rector of the University of Ruse, opened this Round Table. Participants included strategic representatives from the educational sector and social services, who debated for over two hours about how to avoid discrimination in both educational and social institutions.

The ATHENA representatives shared the findings from the Gender Equality audit and assessment of procedures and practices at organisational and national level.

The ATHENA training, under the capacity building for Gender Equality Pan Implementation (GEPI) Committees activities, in 2021, was given special attention as the GEPI Committee at the University of Ruse received high quality information from both international and Bulgarian experts.

The key point of the discussion was how to avoid discrimination. Representatives from the educational sector emphasized that the current culture and national regulations are very supportive of equal rights for females and males in science career development. As a result, the presented GEP was welcomed as a reliable instrument for strengthening and sustaining these achievements regarding female and male tolerance.

The Round Table was held in conjunction with the Sixth Edition of the YOUTH INNOVATION EXPO, where 71 clubs for applied science (mainly from the University of Ruse and regional secondary schools) presented their accomplishments.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The main of the workshop was to start mutual discussion with the stakeholders on the issue of gender equality in research.

4.2 Achievement indicators

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop

According to the project description at least **20** stakeholders are expected to participate this event. We have managed to involve **50** of them, described in Chapter 1.

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion

After the presentation, there was interesting discussion. Most of the participants stood longer to discuss the future challenges.

Indicator #3: Emerging new cooperations

We have managed to discuss mostly with the principals of the Secondary Schools how to keep the equal opportunities of the females and males in science. We have agreed:

- ✓ to have mutual support in replication of the GEP to their institutions whenever they ask us for details.

- ✓ to encourage the joint participation of pupils and students in the YOUTH INNOVATION EXPO, where clubs for applied science (mainly from the University of Ruse and regional secondary schools) present their accomplishments.

4.3 Workshop results

The workshop has been very successful, because we have managed to attract 50 representatives of key organizations, which have strong influence on the development of mentality of tolerance between females and males. The GEP, elaborated under ATHENA project is the first such document in Bulgaria, developed under HORIZON. We consider that the EU support to our educational system very important as we are searching ways to keep the already existing high level of tolerance in Bulgarian science between females and males.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

Media releases in **English**:

Twitter: https://twitter.com/ATHENA_Equality/status/1536663597937577985

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/ATHENAEquality/posts/406045314776063>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6942434550622908418/>

Media releases in **Bulgarian**:

<https://newsfbm.blogspot.com/2022/06/gender-equality-plan-athena-horizon-2020.html>

<https://www.uni-ruse.bg/Faculties/FBM/news>

Conclusion

To achieve some real equal opportunities between females and males we need educational system from the kindergarten till universities. Therefore, it has been a great success that we have involved in this seminar many stakeholders and the next ones are of key importance:

- ✓ The Minister of Education of Bulgaria – Mr. N.Denkov.
- ✓ The Director of the Regional Educational Inspectorate – Mrs. R.Georgieva.
- ✓ 9 Principals of Secondary schools.

- ✓ Representatives of other organizations.

Bulgaria has a very good educational system in terms of tolerance between girls and boys, females and males. We hope that the GEP under ATHENA will be of key importance to keep this national achievement. We proposed our full support to all participants to replicate our GEP to them.

Annexes

This file with general information about GEP shared with all participants:

athena
gender equality to unlock
research potential

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

ПЛАН
за спазване на равните права между жени и мъже в науката (Gender Equality Plan)
в Русенски университет „Ангел Кънчев“ за периода 2022 – 2025 година

Планът за спазване на равните права между жени и мъже в науката (Gender Equality Plan) в Русенски университет „Ангел Кънчев“ е разработен като резултат от Проекта ATHENA (101006416 – ATHENA - H2020 – SwafS-2018 - 2020/H2020 – SwafS – 2020 - 1).

Планът е съобразен с нормативните актове от националното право – Конституция на Република България, Закон за защита от дискриминацията, Закон за равнопоставеност между жените и мъжете (Обн. ДВ. бр.3 3 от 26.04.2016 г.) , както и с актовете от правото на Европейския съюз (равенството между половете е основна ценност на ЕС, основно право и основен принцип на Европейския съюз на социалните права) и с международни договори, по които Република България е страна.

Планът е разработен в съответствие с Националната стратегия за насърчване на равнопоставеността на жените и мъжете 2021–2030 г., приета с Решение на Министерския съвет № 969 от 30 декември 2020 г. и с Националния план за действие за насърчване на равнопоставеността на жените и мъжете за периода 2021-2022 г., като се отчитат спецификите на дейността на РУ „Ангел Кънчев“ като висше училище по смисъла на Закона за висшето образование. Съобразени са и насоките на Европейския институт за равенство между половете за разработване и изпълнение на планове за равенство между жените и мъжете.

Основните цели на плана са:

- чрез изменения и допълнение на вътрешните актове на Университета и осъществяване на различни дейности да се създаде трайна нормативна и институционална среда, която да допринесе за фактическа равнопоставеност на жените и мъжете (студенти, докторанти, административен персонал и академичен състав) в Университета.
- да се осигури провеждането на единна политика на равнопоставеност между жените и мъжете във всички дейности, осъществявани от Университета.
- да се осигури трайна **превенция** срещу пряка и косвена дискриминация въз основа на пола, както и въз основа на други дискриминационни признаци като раса, народност, етническа принадлежност, човешки геном, гражданство, произход, религия или вяра, образование, убеждения, политическа принадлежност, лично или обществено положение, увреждане, възраст, семейно положение, имуществено състояние или на всякакви други признаци, установени в закон или в международен договор, по който Република България е страна.

Приоритетни области:

- равнопоставеност на жените и мъжете при достъпа до образователни услуги, при получаването на научни степени, при заемане на академични длъжности и при сключване на трудови и граждански договори в Русенски университет „Ангел Кънчев“.
- недопускане на разлики по пол при заплащане на възнаграждения, допълнително материално стимулиране и стипендии.
- насърчване на равнопоставеността на жените и мъжете в процесите на вземане на решения в органите за управление на Русенски университет „Ангел Кънчев“ (Общо събрание, Академичен съвет, Ректор, Студентски съвет), както и в органите на управление на основните звена (факултети, филиали, катедри) и обслужващите звена (административни дирекции и отдели).
- борба с насилието и защита и подкрепа на жертвите;
- преодоляване на стереотипите по пол в различни сфери на обществения живот и на сексизма (мерки срещу насилието, основано на пол, включително сексуален тормоз).

За постигане на целите на плана в приоритетните области са разработени мерки за постигане на конкретни резултати, като са описани срокове и отговорни за прилагането на мерките органи на Университета, както индикатори за резултат и оказано въздействие.

SECTION 7. Workshop 1 report of Gobierno De Canarias (GOBCAN, Canary Islands, Spain)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	Gender equality in research and innovation in the Canary islands
Date of the workshop	16/06/2022
Venue of the workshop	The workshop was organized in a hybrid format. Physical address: ACIISI – GOBCAN venue at León y Castillo Street, No. 200. Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain. Virtual room via Webex: link here
Names and positions of the speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Javier Roo Filgueira – Responsible of R&D&I projects at ACIISI-GOBCAN. • Michelle Perello – ATHENA Coordinator. • Ana Lydia Fernández – Coordinator of ‘Opciónate’ Association and external gender expert at ACIISI-GOBCAN. • Patricia Jiménez – Technical at ACIISI-GOBCAN.
Total of number of participants	<p>Total number of all participants: 36 participants Number of participants that attended physically: 21 participants Number of participants that attended online: 15 participants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from ATHENA team: 5 representatives; • Academia and Research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - staff from Research Funding Organizations: 9 - academics from Research Performing Organizations (regional/national): 10 • Government & public sector (policy makers): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the regional authorities: 1 • Industry & business: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of R+D+I related companies: 2

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of enterpris clusters: 2 • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - representatives of the associations and NGO, related to Gender Equity: 4
Participants from the ATHENA partners	Number: 1 from CE

2. Agenda of the workshop

From - To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
9:30 – 9:35	1.Welcome	Javier Roo Filgueira – Responsible of R&D&I projects at ACIISI - GOBCAN
9:35 – 10:00	2.Presentation of the ATHENA project	Michelle Perello – ATHENA Coordinator
10:00 – 10:30	3.Relevance of gender equality to unlock research potential in Canary islands	Ana Lydia – External gender expert at ACIISI-GOBCAN
10:30 – 11:15	4. Measures foreseen in the ACIISI gender equality plan	Patricia Jiménez – Superior Technician at ACIISI-GOBCAN
11:15 – 11:30	Break	
11:30 – 12.15	5.Workshop: Expected impact from the gender equality measures	Facilitator – Michelle Perello
12:15 – 12:30	6.Official closure	

3. General description of the workshop

The event was organized in a hybrid format. Participants that could not attend physically attended online via Webex.

The workshop started with a warm welcome from Javier Roo Filgueira, responsible of R&D&I projects at ACIISI GOBCAN and member of the ATHENA consortium. Then, Michelle Perello, the coordinator of ATHENA, presented the project to the participants. Ana Lydia, external gender expert at ACIISI GOBCAN, gave a speech to raise awareness on how relevant is gender equality in research and innovation and about the unconscious bias and gaps encountered in this field. Patricia Jiménez, technician at ACIISI GOBCAN, presented the diagnosis on gender equality at ACIISI and a preliminary set of measures and actions that will feed the institutional GEP. A joint discussion was held in a final session,

aiming at: 1) identifying other measures that could be included within the GEP; 2) Discussing on the expected impact of the measures presented; and 3) how to facilitate the implementation of the measures.

Stakeholders to be invited were carefully selected (see section of participants to see the type of stakeholders involved), as the objective of the workshop was to get feedback and viewpoints on the proposed measures that will be included within the final draft of the GEP. ACIISI GOBAN is a regional research funding organization in charge of 1) carrying out the responsibilities relating to public policies and programmes in the field of research, technological development and business innovation of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands and its dependent entities; 2) ensuring administrative coordination in the matters assigned to it, in accordance with the guidelines agreed by the Commission for the Coordination of Science, Technology and Innovation, of the bodies and entities of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, and of these with national and international bodies and entities, also acting as an interlocutor. Thus, main stakeholders addressed were both research funding and performing organizations at regional level; beneficiaries of its R&D&I programmes, policies and initiatives (steam/R&D&I related companies, etc.) and civil society and NGO representatives in the field of gender equality and/or R&D&I.

A total of 56 potencial participants were invited to attend the event. Finally, the event counted with a total participation of 36 persons.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The workshop was aimed at discussing with relevant stakeholders the proposed measures to be included within the ACIISI GOBCAN GEP.

4.2 Achievement indicators

Indicator # 1: Enriching debate

Participants contributed with more than 15 valuable comments and viewpoints for the ACIISI GEP measures.

Indicator #2: Attendance

Originally, the event was going to be held physically as the event room had seats limitations. The capacity of the event room full. In order to get maximum attendance of the potential stakeholders identified, the workshop was open to a hybrid format. Finally, 15 stakeholders attended online, which contributed with

valuable comments to the proposed measures to be included in the final version of the institutional GEP of ACIISI.

Indicator #3: Networking

The organization of the event physically was a great opportunity for the participating institutions working in research and innovation in the region of canary islands to meet and take a moment to talk about gender equality with the rest of institutions working in their same field as well as with the associations and NGOs working on GE that were present at the event. Additionally, synergies with the ATHENA project are expected as there was an interchange of experiences and information between the ATHENA representatives and representatives of research institutions responsible for EU projects, which include gender perspectives in their research and innovation activities.

4.3 Workshop results

The cornerstone of this event was the enriching debate that took place during the joint discussion. Attendees were very participative and contributed to the session with useful and valuable comments. Most of the participants that attended the workshop have work experience on gender equality at research and innovation in Canary islands or were members of Commissions of Gender equality within their institutions (for instance, at the event it was present the Director of the Equality Unit at University of La Laguna, the Director of Equality Commission at Institute of Astrophysics of Canary islands (who developed their GEP in the framework of a sister project of ATHENA), members of the Equality Commission at Technological Institute of the Canary islands (ITC), members with experience on GE at Canary islands Oceanic Platform (PLOCAN), among others).

An important aspect discussed was the viability of implementing the proposed measures. From the experiences of the event attendees, their gender strategies include measures that finally can not be effectively implemented due to legal constraints that come from upper legislative framework, which is not adapted to the reality of the institutions and organizations. It was stressed the importance of developing and implementing effective measures.

The main comments raised by participants were the followings:

- Consider that to access funding an evaluation criteria could be if the companies have GEP in place instead of the gender balance of its staff. Request companies if they have looked at equality, and if they have thought about solutions to existing inequalities.
- Come up with measures that are feasible to implement in practice. Assess criteria that depend on the ACIISI and not those that are not under the control of ACIISI.
- To implement awareness raising and training on gender bias in recruitment and to the whole organization.

- Lower the bar for the applicants that are in the recruitment process to be part of evaluation committees for example to women who are not 'cathedratics' but who have a certain number of years of experience in the lower echelon, as they may be equally qualified to evaluate.
- Study the viability of applying blind CVs. To this aim, it is necessary to establish a template and include the gender perspective in all the recruitment process.
- For research positions and grants awarding, stays in prestigious centres, travels, etc. are highly valued, and there are women and men who do not have the possibility of doing stays due to work-life balance constraints (care responsibilities, for instance).
- It might be considered to set a standard to ensure that applicants have the knowledge, skills and competences necessary to do the research/job. From there, quality criteria might be reviewed; what may be a point of 6 for a man is a point of 7 for a woman.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

Figure 6. Michelle Perello presenting the ATHENA project

Figure 7. Ana Lidia Fernández talking about the relevance of gender equality to unlock research potential

Figure 8. Patricia Jiménez presenting the foreseen measures within the gender equality plan (GEP) of ACIISI GOBCAN

Figure 9. Joint discussion on the expected impact of the measures foreseen within the ACIISI-GOBCAN GEP

SECTION 8. Workshop 1 report of Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT, Azores, Portugal)

1. Participants

Title of the workshop	“The Importance of Gender Equality Plans in European Research and Innovation (R&I) Programs Funding”
Date of the workshop	29/09/2022
Venue of the workshop	Online via GoToMeeting (https://meet.goto.com/895181477)
Names and positions of the speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gisela Nascimento - Member of the Board, FRCT • Carolina Bettencourt – Project Manager, FRCT • Paulo Fontes – Gender Expert, University of the Azores
Total number of participants	<p>Total number of participants: 37</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of representatives from the ATHENA team: 3 • Research organisations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Staff from Research Funding Organisations: 6 • Government & public sector (policymakers): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Representatives of the regional authorities: 6 • Industry & business: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Representatives of Research, Development and Innovation (R+D+I) related companies: 13 • Civil society: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Representatives of the associations related to Gender Equity: 5 • Other: 4
Participants from the ATHENA project partners	As it was a local workshop organised by FRCT, there were no other ATHENA project partners present.

2. Agenda of the workshop

From - To	Activity	Speaker/Moderator
14:00 – 14:10	Welcome Session	Gisela Nascimento // Member of the Board (FRCT)
14:10 – 14:30	“Challenges of Gender Equality in Research and Innovation from Europe to the Azores”	Paulo Fontes // Gender Expert (University of the Azores)
14:30 – 14:50	Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 ATHENA Project FRCT Gender Equality Plan	Carolina Bettencourt // Project Manager (FRCT)
14:50 – 15:10	“How to apply Gender Equality Plans in entities?”	Paulo Fontes // Gender Expert (University of the Azores)
15:10 – 15:30	Group dynamic: Experiences in the development and implementation of Gender Equality Plans	Paulo Fontes // Gender Expert (University of the Azores)
15:30 – 15:40	Final Considerations	Gisela Nascimento // Member of the Board (FRCT)

3. General description of the workshop

The virtual workshop "The Importance of Gender Equality Plans in European Research and Innovation (R&I) Programs Funding" was held on September 29, 2022, in Ponta Delgada, Azores, Portugal, as part of Task 6.2 "Stakeholder Engagement at Local Level" of the ATHENA project.

The regional stakeholders who were invited were carefully chosen since one of the workshop's objectives was to share project results and achievements with key actors and obtain feedback from stakeholders in order to potentially transfer developed and implemented gender equality (GE) actions.

The event was attended by representatives of the FRCT ATHENA team and the FRCT GEPI Committee. Research organisations such as the University of the Azores, and policymakers at the regional level as the Regional Directorate for the Promotion of Equality and Social Inclusion (DRPIIS). Also, representatives of the public sector such as City Councils, R+D+I-related companies and relevant regional associations related to gender equity such as APF-Açores - Association for Family Planning and Sexual and Reproductive Health, UMAR-Açores - Association for Equality and Women's Rights, ACEESA - Association Centre for Solidarity Economy Studies of the Atlantic, and CRESAÇOR - Regional Cooperative of Solidarity Economy. There were thirty-seven participants in total at the event. Thus, research funding and performing organisations, policymakers and regional authorities, R+D+I-related businesses and GE-affiliated associations were the key target audiences.

GEPs have become a mandatory eligibility criterion for public bodies and public or private institutions of higher education or research, seeking funding from the Horizon Europe Programme. In this sense, FRCT's goal was to introduce GEPs as an excellent tool to promote GE in an organisation but also to inform stakeholders of this mandatory requirement for European funding. FRCT presented its GEP as a practical example in order to share challenges, solutions, and best/bad practices encountered during its development.

Gisela Nascimento, FRCT board member, opened the session and presented the agenda. Paulo Fontes, one member of the gender expert group of the University of the Azores, provided an overview of the main GE challenges in R&I from Europe to the Azores. In this speech, the GE directives adopted by the European Union in various areas were addressed, along with the communitarian principle of EU law and its direct impact on EU citizens and GE. The role of the Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality in Portugal, the National Strategy for Equality and Nondiscrimination, and the Portuguese government's definition of three action plans for GE strategies and 2030 objectives were mentioned in the Portuguese context. In addition, the impact of COVID-19 pandemic measures on women's academic careers, the findings of Elsevier's 2020 gender report, the implementation of GEPs in the field of education, and the need for innovative approaches bridging various fields in gender studies were discussed.

Carolina Bettencourt, ATHENA project manager, introduced the GE Strategy 2020-2025 as well as the ATHENA project, the FRCT GEP and the process involved in its development. The Strategy outlines policy objectives and actions that will allow Europe to make significant progress toward gender equality by 2025. The goal is to create a Union in which women and men, girls and boys, in all their diversity, are free to choose their life paths, have equal opportunities, and can equally participate in and lead European society. In this context, the purpose of the presentation was to describe the GE eligibility criteria for Horizon Europe funding and how the ATHENA project supports the development and implementation of the FRCT GEP serving as a model for other regional institutions.

Paulo Fontes addressed in its second talk, the major guidelines on how to implement GEPs across organisations, detailing the steps involved in this process and the EU thematic areas, as well as providing examples of guides for the elaboration of this type of document and general recommendations. Lastly, there was room for a group dynamic activity and discussion concerning experiences in the development and implementation of the GEPs.

The participation of the Regional Directorate for the Promotion of Equality and Social Inclusion along with several regional entities in the area of equality and inclusion of women in society helped bring the topic closer and foster a space for dialogue about the difficulties involved in the preparation and implementation of GEPs within regional organisations.

4. Description of how the objectives of the workshop were reached

4.1 Objectives of the workshop

The primary objective of the workshop was to raise awareness of the importance of GE in RFOs, RPOs, and other institutions, present the ATHENA project, share the challenges and tools encountered during the development of the FRCT GEP, and outline the actions that will be implemented following the adoption of the Plan.

Furthermore, FRCT pretended to promote dialogue among institutions about what it means to achieve GE in Science, particularly in regional institutions. The ultimate goal was to encourage stakeholder involvement in the ATHENA project so that its outcomes can be replicated in other relevant entities.

4.2 Achievement indicators

Indicator # 1: Attendance of the workshop

Thirty-seven individuals attended the workshop, representatives from the ATHENA team and FRCT GEPI committee, researchers and staff from research organisations, representatives of the regional authorities, representatives of R+D+I-related companies and representatives of the associations related to Gender Equity. Therefore, the attendance exceeded the established number in the indicator.

Indicator #2: Emerging a discussion

Following the presentations, the entities engaged in an interesting debate. The dichotomous nature of the world and the gendered divisions were both significant and fascinating aspects of the various topics that were covered in the discussion. It was said that "gendered segregation begins in the separation of girls' and boys' toys on store shelves and extends to those seen in the workplace and society." This is a reference to a statement that was made.

The vast majority of participants indicated that they were interested in the GE topic and were willing to advocate for it. The institutions addressed the significance of promoting GE in the Azores to change mentalities, with the implementation of GEPs as one possible strategy among the many that were discussed.

Indicator #3: Networking

The organisation of the event provided FRCT and the participating research institutions with an excellent opportunity to meet with other institutions in the field and discuss GE. In addition, synergies with the ATHENA project are anticipated as a result of the information and experience exchange between the ATHENA team and representatives of regional institutions working to integrate gender perspectives into their activities.

4.3 Workshop results

The virtual workshop was a success, as FRCT was able to bring together thirty-seven representatives from influential organisations that can help foster a more accepting culture among men and women.

The event benefited FRCT because it provided an opportunity to bring the GE topic closer and foster a dialogue about the challenges involved in developing and implementing GEPs in regional organisations.

The most significant aspect of this event was the enlightening conversation that took place during the joint discussion. Attendees were highly involved and contributed insightful and useful comments to the session. Everyone agreed that a GEP is a good starting point for transcending gender.

5. Pictures of the workshop and media releases

Figure 10- Carolina Bettencourt presenting the GE Strategy 2022-2025

Figure 11- Paulo Fontes discussing the development and implementation of GEPs in the entities

Figure 12- Group dynamic: Experiences in the development and implementation of GEPs

The event was promoted through the FRCT's social media channels and website using the links provided below:

- http://frct.azores.gov.pt/en/noticia/wk_athena/
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/frctazores_frctazores-genderequality-igualdadedegenero-activity-6980501618915987456-sl6J?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/frctazores_athenaequality-activity-6980926900449763328-mY2?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- <https://twitter.com/FRCTAzores/status/1574736086714437632>

In addition, the workshop was disseminated via ATHENA's website and social media:

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research potential

- <https://www.athenaequality.eu/news/frct-hosted-a-virtual-workshop-entitled-the-importance-of-gender-equality-plans-in-european-ri-programs-funding/>
- https://twitter.com/ATHENA_Equality/status/1575887303368933376
- <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6981655510693367808>
- <https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=479762404071020&set=a.332614928785769>
- <https://t.me/joinchat/ptv6QBdJYS80NTQ0>

Conclusion remarks

This workshop helped to raise awareness about the importance of GEP development for EU funding but especially for GE progress in Azores Region.

Some entities in the Azores already have a GEP, while other institutions plan to implement one in order to promote equality among their members. Either way, all present entities benefited from the exchange of best or bad practices of FRCT's GEP development to start developing their GEPs or to improve them.

FRCT has observed that a significant number of organisations are concentrating their efforts not only on diversity, equality, and inclusion but also on a feeling of belonging. In this sense, FRCT is fully behind all of the participants' GEP development efforts, and it has high hopes that the GEP that was developed under ATHENA will play a significant part in ensuring that this regional achievement is maintained.

Annexes

GOVERNO
DOS AÇORES

FRCT
FUNDO REGIONAL DA CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA

Workshop ATHENA

A importância do Plano de Igualdade de Género na captação de financiamento externo em programas europeus de I&I

29 de setembro de 2022 (14:00 – 15:40 AZOT)
Online via GoToMeeting

Convite

Exmas. Senhoras,
Exmos. Senhores,

O Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT) tem o prazer de convidar a vossa instituição a participar no Workshop online: **“A importância do Plano de Igualdade de Género na captação de financiamento externo em programas europeus de I&I”**, no próximo dia **29 de setembro**, às **14h00**, no âmbito do projeto europeu ATHENA, financiado pelo programa Horizonte 2020 e do qual o FRCT é parceiro.

O Plano de Igualdade de Género tornou-se um requisito obrigatório para qualquer financiamento do programa Horizonte Europa para candidatos de organismos públicos e de instituições de ensino superior ou de investigação pública, ou privada.

Com este workshop, o FRCT pretende promover a importância da elaboração dos Planos de Igualdade de Género em organizações de desenvolvimento e financiamento de Investigação, bem como em instituições de outras áreas, públicas e privadas. O Plano para a Igualdade de Género do FRCT, elaborado no âmbito do projeto ATHENA, será apresentado como exemplo prático, como o intuito de partilhar os desafios, soluções e boas práticas encontradas durante o seu desenvolvimento. Durante o Workshop haverá um espaço de diálogo, sobre os desafios na elaboração e implementação de Plano de Igualdade de Género nas organizações.

Gostaríamos de solicitar a participação de um representante da vossa instituição que possa contribuir para o diálogo sobre este importante tópico.

Inscrição registo:
<https://bit.ly/3C6nixD>

Com os melhores cumprimentos,

Bruno Marques Teixeira
Presidente do Conselho Diretivo do FRCT

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Figure 13- Invitation Letter to the Stakeholders